

Stem Cell Research: Lab Resources

Generation of Mucopolysaccharidosis type II (MPS II) human induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) line from a 7-year-old male with pathogenic IDS mutation

Eszter Varga^a, Csilla Nemes^a, István Bock^a, Norbert Varga^b, Anita Fehér^a, Julianna Kobolák^a, András Dinnyés^{a,c,*}

^a BioTalentum Ltd., Gödöllő, Hungary

^b Department of Metabolic Diseases, Heim Pál Children's Hospital, Budapest, Hungary

^c Molecular Animal Biotechnology Laboratory, Szent István University, Gödöllő, Hungary

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ABSTRACT

Peripheral blood was collected from a 7-year-old male patient with an X-linked recessive mutation of Iduronate 2-sulfatase (IDS) gene (NM_000202.7(IDS):c.182C>T) causing MPS II (OMIM 309900). Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were reprogrammed by lentiviral delivery of a self-silencing hOKSM polycistronic vector. The pluripotency of the iPSC line was confirmed by the expression of pluripotency-associated markers and *in vitro* spontaneous differentiation towards the 3 germ layers. The iPSC line showed normal karyotype. The cell line offers a good platform to study MPS II pathophysiology, for drug testing, early biomarker discovery and gene therapy studies.

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Resource Table:

Name of stem cell line	MPSII-4.1
Institution	BioTalentum Ltd.
Person who created resource	Prof. András Dinnyés, Eszter Varga
Contact person and email	andras.dinnyes@biotalentum.hu
Date archived/stock date	May, 2013
Origin	Peripheral blood mononuclear cells
Type of resource	Induced pluripotent stem cell; derived from a patient with hemizygous NM_000202.7(IDS):c.182C>T mutation.
Sub-type	Induced pluripotent stem cell
Key transcription factors	OCT3/4, KLF4, SOX2, C-MYC
Authentication	Identity and purity of the cell line was confirmed by: Sanger sequencing of the pathogenic mutation, expression analysis of dTomato and pluripotency markers, <i>in vitro</i> differentiation potential, karyotyping
Link to related literature	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/20385817 http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3070104/ http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18038146
Information in public databases	N/A
Ethics	Patient informed consent obtained/ Ethics Review Board- competent authority approval obtained

Resource details

Peripheral blood was collected from a 7-year-old male patient with genetically characterized MPS II disorder diagnosed by Department of Pediatrics, University of Pécs (Hungary). Based on the clinical symptoms of the patient, the disorder was determined to be mild MPS II. The patient carries a pathogenic, X-linked, hemizygous mutation of the IDS gene (NM_000202.7(IDS):c.182C>T, p.Ser61Phe). The single nucleotide variation (SNV) results an amino acid change with deleterious effect on the Iduronate 2-sulfatase enzyme function and to the accumulation of glycosaminoglycans. Mutations of IDS gene have been shown to cause MPS II disorder (Wraith et al. 2008). In the patient-derived iPSCs the presence of the pathogenic mutation was confirmed by Sanger sequencing of the PCR product harboring the SNV (Table 1, Fig. 1A).

To generate the MPSII-4.1 iPSC line the pRRL.PPT.SF.hOKSMco.idTomato.preFRT lentiviral vector was used, which was shown that under certain condition is self-silencing shortly after transduction (Voelkel et al. 2010; Warlich et al. 2011). The iPSC-like colonies were picked 18–21 days post-transduction and one stable line was maintained named: MPSII-4.1 which was expanded for further examination.

The pluripotency of MPSII-4.1 line was confirmed by alkaline phosphatase staining (ALP) and by immunocytochemistry staining (ICC) for endogenous NANOG and E-CADHERIN (Fig. 1B) after silencing of the exogenous hOKSM construct.

The *in vitro* spontaneous differentiation potential of the iPSC line towards the three germ layers was demonstrated by the expression of ectodermal (β III-TUBULIN), mesodermal (BRACHYURY) and endodermal (GATA4) markers (Fig. 1B) using ICC.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: andras.dinnyes@biotalentum.hu (A. Dinnyés).

Table 1
Primers used in the study.

Gene symbol	Nucleotide change	Protein change	Fwd and Rvs primers (5' - 3')	PCR product (bp)
IDS	c.182C>T (NM_000202.7)	p.Ser61Phe	CCTTGGGCCTCTTAGTAACC CTTCTGACACCAGGCAAG	517

The karyotype of the MPSII-4.1 iPSC line was determined by Giemsa-banding, proving normal diploid 46, XY karyotype, without any detectable abnormalities (Fig. 1B).

Materials and methods

Experimental procedures

The chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and all the culture reagents from Thermo Fisher Scientific, unless otherwise specified.

Cell culture

All cells were cultured at 37 °C in humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. The iPSCs were cultured on Matrigel (BD Biosciences) in mTeSR-1 medium (Stem Cell Technologies) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Reprogramming of PBMCs

PBMCs were isolated using the Vacutainer® CPT™ Cell Preparation Tube with Sodium Heparin (BD Biosciences). PBMCs were seeded (1×10^6 cells) in Expansion Medium (EM): QBSF-60 medium (Quality Biological) supplemented with 50 µg/ml Ascorbic acid, 1% Pen/Strep, 50 ng/ml SCF (R&D systems), 10 ng/ml IL-3 (R&D systems), 2 U/ml EPO (R&D systems), 40 ng/ml IGF-1 (R&D systems) and 1 µM Dexamethasone. Three days later the cells were transduced with pRRL.PPT.SF.hOKSMco.idTomato.preFRT (Voelkel et al. 2010; Warlich et al. 2011) vector using conventional lentivirus transduction at 0,2–0,4 MOI. Three days post-transduction the cells were seeded onto Mitomycin C treated-MEF in IMDM MEF medium (IMDM, 10% FBS, 1% 100× MEM Non-Essential Amino Acid Solution, 0.1 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 1% Pen/Strep) supplemented with 50 µg/ml Ascorbic acid and growth factors applied in EM medium. From day seven post-transduction cells were cultured in HESC medium: DMEM/F12, 20% Knockout Serum Replacement, 1% 100× MEM Non-Essential Amino Acid Solution, 0.1 mM β-mercaptoethanol, 0.5% Pen/Strep, 10 ng/ml bFGF, supplemented

A

B

Fig. 1. Characterization of MPSII-4.1 iPSC line. A) Sanger sequencing of the region containing the NM_000202.7 (IDS):c.182C>T SNV in the newly established iPSC line. B) Top: Morphology of the generated iPSC (4×), the iPSC line showed Alkaline Phosphatase activity (ALP) (10×) and was positive for pluripotency-associated markers: NANOG (20×), E-CADHERIN (40×) (in green), nucleus was labelled with DAPI (in blue). Bottom: Spontaneous differentiation potential (Day 14) was confirmed by ICC for mesodermal (BRACHYURY), ectodermal (βIII-TUBULIN) and endodermal (GATA4) germ layers (40×) (in green), the nucleus was labelled with DAPI (in blue), karyogram showing normal 46 chromosomes (XY).

Table 2
Antibodies used in this study.

	Manufacturer	Dilution
Pluripotency markers		
Mouse anti-E-Cadherin (human)	Thermo Fischer Sci.	1/1000
Goat anti-hNanog	R&D Systems	1/50
Three germ layer markers		
Rabbit anti- β III-Tubulin	Covance	1/2000
Rabbit anti-BrachyuryT	Santa Cruz	1/50
Mouse anti-GATA4	Santa Cruz	1/50
Secondary antibodies		
Alexa Fluor 488 donkey anti-goat IgG	Thermo Fischer Sci.	1/2000
Alexa Fluor 488 donkey anti-mouse IgG	Thermo Fischer Sci.	1/2000
Alexa Fluor 488 donkey anti-rabbit IgG	Thermo Fischer Sci.	1/2000

with 50 μ g/ml Ascorbic acid. The appeared ES-like colonies were manually picked (Day 18–21) and cultured as iPSCs thereafter.

Alkaline phosphatase staining

Following 4% PFA fixation the cells were incubated with ALP solution for 30 min at RT. The stained cells were observed under inverted microscope. The ALP solution consisted of 29.7 mM TRIS base and 6 mM maleic acid (Fluka) pH 8.5–9.0; supplemented with 0.08% MgCl₂, 10.8 mM Naphthol-As MX Phosphate and 23 μ M Fast Red TR Salt.

Immunocytochemistry staining

The expression of specific pluripotency and germ layer markers were analyzed using conventional ICC staining. The cells were fixed in 4% PFA. The antibodies and applied dilutions are listed in Table 2. The cells were observed under fluorescent microscope equipped with 3D imaging module (AxioImager system with ApoTome, Carl Zeiss) controlled by AxioVision 4.8.1 Microscope software (Carl Zeiss).

Karyotyping

Cells were treated with Demecolcine solution (10 μ g/ml in HBSS), and processed with standard methods. Giemsa-banded karyotype was performed and a minimum of 20 metaphases were analyzed. The chromosomes were classified according to the International System for Human Cytogenetic Nomenclature (ISCN).

Sanger sequencing

To confirm the presence of the pathogenic IDS mutation in the newly established iPSC line PCR primers were designed to the region of interest (Table 1). PCR reactions were performed using Phusion Hot Start II High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase and MPSII-4.1 gDNA as the template. The PCR product was purified with GenElute PCR cleanup kit and sequenced directly using an ABI Prism 3130xl Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA) and BigDye Terminator Cycle Sequencing v3.1 Kit (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA).

In vitro spontaneous differentiation

Cell clumps were cultured in suspension for five days in mTeSR-1. The formed EBs were plated on 0.1% gelatin covered cover slips in differentiation medium: DMEM, 20% FBS, 1% 100 \times MEM Non-Essential Amino Acid Solution, 0.1 mM β -mercaptoethanol, 1% Pen/Strep. The cells were fixed on day 14 of differentiation with 4% PFA and stained for the 3 germ layer markers (Table 2).

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